

Figure S2: Summary of the information regarding *A. thaliana* experiments.

a) Pipeline followed in the experiments with *A. thaliana*.

T0

T1

DsRED(+)

DsRED(-)

Used as reference in
WGS experiment

PDS3 deletion
(Fig. 5b)

Chimeric
plants

T2

DsRED(+)

DsRED(-)

Fig. 2Sd

Fig. 5c, 5d, 2Sc

T3

Fig. 2Se

b) White spots found in the cotyledons (left) and leaves (right) of DsRED(+) T1 lines compatible with *PDS3* deletion.

T1 seedlings (cotyledons)

T1 plants (leaves)

c) Large deletions and re-arrangements found in pools of white and green T2 seedlings of PDS-1,2,3 lines.

At4g14210 (*PDS3*)

d) Mutations found in DsRED(-) T2 PDS-1 and PDS-3 plants. The highlighted plants were selected for Whole Genome Sequencing to perform the off-targets experiments. “Del” stands for deletion, “ins” for insertion. When heterozygous both alleles are separated by slash.

DsRED(-) Plants	Mutations	
	Target 1	Target 2
PDS-1-32	del6	wt
PDS-1-33	wt/del8	wt
PDS-1-34	del4/del6	wt
PDS-1-35	del6	wt
PDS-1-38	del4	wt/del3
PDS-1-40	wt/del8	wt/ins22
PDS-1-41	del81	wt/del3
PDS-1-55	del4/del6	wt/del3
PDS-1-116	del4/del7	wt
PDS-1-117	del11/del34	wt
PDS-1-118	del5/del1773	wt
PDS-1-119	del6	wt
PDS-1-120	del10/del42	wt
PDS-1-121	wt/del17	wt
PDS-1-122	wt/del9	wt
PDS-1-123	del7/del10	wt
PDS-3-56	wt	wt
PDS-3-59	wt/del1265	wt
PDS-3-60	wt/del17	wt
PDS-3-61	del4/del1265	wt
PDS-3-62	wt	wt
PDS-3-63	wt/del17	wt
PDS-3-64	wt/del1265	wt
PDS-3-65	wt	wt
PDS-3-108	del7/del17	wt/del3
PDS-3-109	wt	wt
PDS-3-110	del7/del17	wt
PDS-3-111	wt/del1265	wt
PDS-3-112	wt	wt
PDS-3-113	wt/del1265	wt
PDS-3-114	wt/del17	wt
PDS-3-115	del17	wt

e) Segregation analysis of the DsRED(-) T3 seeds. Table 1 shows the green:albino seedlings ratio and Table 2 the no-deletion:deletion ratio.

Table 1:
green:albino ratio

Plant T2	Phenotype seeds T3			Expected ratio 3:1		χ^2	Hypothesis
	Green	White	No germinated	Green	White	<i>p-value</i>	3:1
PDS-1-111	85	13	3	74	25	0.0073	Discarded
PDS-1-113	85	8	0	70	23	0.0003	Discarded
PDS11-118	116	20	4	102	34	0.0056	Discarded

Table 2:
no-deletion:deletion ratio

Plant T2	Seeds T3 - Presence Large Deletion		Expected ratio 1:2		χ^2	Hypothesis
	No presence	Presence	No presence	Presence	<i>p-value</i>	1:2
PDS-1-118	6	18	8	16	0.3865	Approved